

Cascadia Region Earthquake Science Center

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Assessing Tomographic Models of the Cascadia Region Using Short to Intermediate Period Spectral Element Waveform Simulations

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CRESCENT SEED Grant Final Report: “*Assessing Tomographic Models of the Cascadia Region Using Short to Intermediate Period Spectral Element Waveform Simulations*”

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1) Introduction

The primary goal of this project was to establish a framework for validating tomographic models of the Cascadia region using physics-based simulations of short to intermediate period waveforms from both earthquakes and ambient noise, which would i) help evaluate how well previous regional tomography models are capable of fitting seismic waveform data, and ii) provide a metric for evaluating different generations of the Community Velocity Model (CVM) that is in development by CRESCENT. As part of this effort, a reference data set of earthquake waveforms and ambient noise correlation functions (NCFs) for comparing models was created, and forward simulations were performed for a set of regional tomography models. Below I describe the project outcomes from this research and discuss future directions.

2) Reference Data Set Selection

One of the challenges of developing a reference data set for the Cascadia region is the relative lack of seismicity. To overcome the limited number of earthquake – receiver paths, I used vertical component NCFs from virtual sources in addition to regional earthquakes. The NCFs here shared with me by Bin He and are included in the data set that was used to develop the Generation 0 CRESCENT CVM.

The selection of earthquakes and virtual sources for a reference data set is subjective, although an optimal reference data set should include diverse ray path coverage and abundant waveforms with high signal to noise ratio (SNR). Here, I considered only earthquakes with $M_w > 6$ that occurred since 2000-01-01. From these, an initial quality control check was performed based on visual inspection of vertical component record sections, and 10 events were selected based on waveform quality, station abundance, and geographic diversity, including off-shore ray path coverage. Similar considerations were made when selecting virtual sources. The events selected for the reference data set are shown in Figure 1 and include 10 regional earthquakes and 10 virtual sources.

Once the events were selected, I calculated signal to noise ratio for vertical component waveforms at each station for all events and kept only those with $SNR > 10$. The signal was calculated in a 100 s window that moved out with a velocity of 3.0 km/s in order to capture the fundamental mode Rayleigh wave. In the case of earthquakes, the noise window was a 100 s window of pre-event noise, starting 100 s before the event origin. In the case of virtual sources, the 100 s noise window for NCFs started 1400 s after the ‘origin time’ (i.e., the zero lag time) because there is no appropriate pre-event noise window, and it is desirable to not include any energy that arrives near zero lag. The SNR was calculated as the RMS amplitude of the signal window divided by the RMS amplitude of the noise window. All waveforms were filtered between 10 – 35 s prior to calculating SNR. SNR could be calculated in multiple frequency bands, but here, for simplicity, only one band was used.

Figure 1. Events chosen for the reference data set. Red stars indicate earthquakes, and blue dots indicate virtual events used for NCFs.

3) Forward Modeling

The proposed work aimed to assess 5 different tomography models (Table 1). However, several changes were made to this plan. First, I decided against analyzing the model by Bodmer et al., (2020). This was primarily because the model is based on finite frequency tomography of body wave travel times, and as such would not be expected to perform well at matching Rayleigh wave observations, which are primarily considered in this study. Additionally, the model is described in relative velocity perturbation, making it more challenging to implement. It may be of interest to see how models based on body wave travel times compare to those that include surface wave data, but that is left for future work. Second, I did not include the model by Delph et al., (2018) in the analysis. This is because the methodology used to create this model (joint inversion of receiver functions and surface wave dispersion) is similar to the method used to develop the Gen0 CRESCENT CVM. By the time I started work on this project, the Gen0 CRESCENT CVM was nearing completion, so I decided I would substitute the Delph et al., (2018) model with the Gen 0 model. My analysis of the Gen 0 model is ongoing. Lastly, rather than using the WUS256 model of Rodgers et al., (2022), I used an updated version of this model (WUS324; Rodgers et al., 2024). The result of these changes is that I analyzed 3 models instead of the initial plan of 5.

Model	Type	Data used	Method	Period	Reference
Cascadia_ANT+R F_Delph2018	Vs	Broadband, 1993-94, 2005-2016	Ambient noise/ receiver functions	8 – 50 s	Delph et al., (2018)
WUS256	Vp,Vs	Broadband data, 72 regional events	Adjoint tomography	T > 20 s	Rodgers et al., (2022)
BODMER_VPVS	Vp,Vs	Teleseismic travel times, on land +offshore stations	Cascadia	Finite-frequency tomography	~1 – 10 s
CASCADE_ANT2014	Vs	Broadband data between 1995-2012	Full-wave ambient noise tomography	7 – 200 s	Gao & Shen (2014)
3D-CVM_V1.6	Vp,Vs	Compilation of tomographic models	Prescribed wave speeds	-	Stephenson et al., (2017)

Table 1. Proposed tomography models that will be used to assess short to intermediate period waveform fits of body and surface waves in the Cascadia Region.

For each of these three models analyzed (CASC1.6, CASCADE_ANT2014, and WUS324), forward simulations for the 20 events in the reference data set were performed using the spectral element-based code Specfem3D Globe (Komatitsch & Tromp, 2002). The simulation domain was a spherical chunk centered on [44°, -118°], spanning 22° in latitude and longitude and extending to a depth of 660 km. Tomographic models were obtained in NetCDF format from either the IRIS EarthScope EMC repository or the CRESCENT CVM website (<https://cvm.cascadiaquakes.org/>). Models were incorporated on to the mesh using Specfem3D’s `model EMC` routine. This routine does not naturally work for all models in the EMC repository because it requires absolute seismic wave speed and density and specific variable names which may differ from the meta data in the NetCDF files. Thus, for each of the three models, I wrote python scripts to write new NetCDF files that are compatible with the `model EMC` routine. These scripts can be modified and used to implement any NetCDF formatted tomography model, including different generations of the CRESCENT CVM. Cross sections of shear wave speed from the computational meshes, which were accurate to a minimum period of 5 s, are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. V_S cross sections through Specfem3D meshes for each of the three models tested. The top row shows a horizontal slice at 50 km depth, and the bottom row shows a vertical slice at a latitude of 44°. Mesh slices were extracted using Specfem3D’s `xcreate_cross_section` function.

For all three models, forward simulations for each earthquake in the reference data set were calculated using the globalCMT moment tensor solution. For virtual sources, vertical component NCFs were simulated using a vertical point force. Figure 3 shows examples of vertical component record sections calculated for event 20221220_103424, using the tomography model of Rodgers et al. (2024).

Figure 3. Comparison between observed (black) and synthetic (red) vertical component waveforms of event 20221220_103424. Waveforms are filtered between 5 – 20 s in the left panel and 20 – 40 s in the right panel. Synthetics were calculated using the WUS324 model.

4) Model Evaluation

To assess the misfit between observed and synthetic waveforms, we calculate both cross correlation travel time shift and correlation coefficient. Prior to misfit calculation, waveforms are bandpass filtered and normalized based by the maximum of the absolute value of the signal. The correlation coefficient is calculated after waveform alignment (i.e., after shifting the synthetic waveform by the calculated lag time). Only observed waveforms with SNR > 10 are considered. In principle, for earthquakes, additional misfit metrics could be used, such as the L2-norm of the difference between waveforms. Here, we choose not to calculate amplitude dependent misfit metrics due to the tradeoff between the model and optimum moment tensor solution.

Figure 4 shows an example of misfit metrics calculated for each of the three models, for all earthquake events. In period bands of 20 – 40 s and (Fig. 4 A and B) and 5 – 20 s (Fig. 4C and D) the model WUS324 performs the best for all metrics considered, although at higher frequency, the differences are more subtle. At 20 – 40 s period, WUS324 has the lowest mean lag time and standard deviation (0.7 s +/- 7.3 s for WUS324 compared to -1.2 s +/- 9.2 s for CASCADE_ANT2014 and 2.8 s +/- 8.2 s for CASC1.6). Additionally, the L2 norm of the lag times is substantially lower for WUS324 compared to other models (360 s for WUS324, compared to 422 s for CASCADE_ANT2014 and 407 s for CASC1.6). The better performance of WUS324 for these events is perhaps not surprising considering that it is based on fitting waveforms from local earthquakes (likely including some events used in the reference data set), but it does suggest that adjoint inversion of regional earthquakes could be an important component of improving resolution of subsequent generations of the CRESCENT CVM.

Figure 4. Histograms of lag times and correlation coefficients calculated for each model filtered between 20 – 40 s (top row) and 5 – 20 s (bottom row) for all earthquakes considered. The maximum allowed lag time is 20 s and the minimum allowed correlation coefficient is 0.5. The mean and standard deviation of the distributions are reported for each model in the top of every panel.

5) Products

This work, at various stages of progress, has been presented at CRESCENT teleconferences, including at CVM working group meetings. Additionally, I will be presenting the work at the upcoming AGU Fall Meeting, 2025. On completion of the analysis of the Gen 0 CVM model, I plan on preparing a manuscript for submission to a peer-reviewed journal.

6) Future Directions

In addition to the evaluation of the Gen 0 model, there are several tasks that remain to be completed. First, the models implemented in Specfem3D Globe are superposed on a 1D background model, which can lead to sharp edges at the boundaries of where the 3D models are defined. To test the importance of artificial boundaries on results, I am working with Rasheed Ajala, who developed a tool to smoothly merge models described at multiple scales. Additionally, although here I am reporting average misfit statistics for all events considered, I am working on analyzing the spatial variability of misfit metrics, which can help guide our understanding of which regions of models are more poorly resolved than others. Finally, although outside of the scope of this work, I believe that benchmarking tests should be performed to test the importance of explicitly meshing the liquid water layer, versus using a simplified ocean load approximation. This may be especially important to consider in the context of using full waveform inversion to iteratively improve the CRESCENT CVM.

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